

Trends in Pediatric Palliative Care Research (TPPCR) 2025; Special Edition 3 – Oncology:

Reflection on Tributes: An important form of Communication for Clinicians

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Abstract:

This TPPCR commentary discusses the 2025 Oncology citation list and comments on what is missing, literature about patient tributes and how important this form of communication is for Clinicians.

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Reflection on Tributes: An important form of Communication for Clinicians

In pediatric palliative care, enhanced communication is a core competency and a skill we use daily when having difficult conversations with patients and families. This month's list exemplifies how communication is one of the most important and widely discussed themes in pediatric oncology and palliative care, with a growing body of literature exploring how clinicians navigate conversations about delivering bad news¹, prognostication^{2,3}, and end of life⁴.

However, the way we communicate the death of a patient is a form of communication which is often overlooked in the literature yet can be especially meaningful to the clinician and team who care for the patient. My experiences as a pediatric oncologist and palliative care clinician have led me to reflect more broadly on communication surrounding death itself, and how it continues even after a child has died.

Working across both oncology and pediatric palliative care has shown me how differently the death of a child is communicated within each setting. At Canuck Place Children's Hospice, the moment a child dies, an email is sent to the entire team, clinical and non-clinical alike. It is a ritual that has existed for years, a way of acknowledging the significance of the loss and ensuring that no one learns of it by accident or delay. When I first arrived as a fellow, coming from oncology, I was already familiar with many of the children who died at the hospice. I found myself wanting to share more than the basic demographic details traditionally included in these notifications. I wanted the team to remember the child as I had known them, their uniqueness, their passions, the small joys that defined them far more than their illness. Over time, these emails evolved from simple announcements into tributes. It also became unexpectedly therapeutic for me, a way for me to process the intimate and intense journey that I had just been a part of.

The communication process after a child's death in oncology is different. An email is sent to the clinical team, sometimes days after the child has died, primarily for record keeping. It contains the essential facts about the diagnosis but not a lot about who the child was as a person. In discussions with my oncology colleagues, especially the bedside nurses who have such close relationships with these patients, to learn of the child's death with such impersonal communication can feel wrong. Not knowing the circumstances of the child's last days or hours, who was present and how the child died can feel unsettling to those who knew them well. These conversations with my colleagues made me think about how important it is for teams who invest deeply in their patients to have timely, meaningful acknowledgment of a loss.

Reflecting on these differences has led me to ask: what is a tribute, and why does it matter. To me, a tribute is a form of communication that is more than just a summary. It is a gesture of compassion and remembrance. It captures who the child was as a human being, not just their diagnosis. It allows us to talk about their favourite songs, the way they lit up when their sibling entered the room, the stuffed animal they insisted on bringing to every appointment. Writing these tributes has also been beneficial and healing for me as a clinician. Reflecting on these experiences has allowed me to think about what went well, what I would do differently next time and has allowed me to heal and find closure. Writing can provide us with an outlet that is often under recognized but necessary to build resilience in this field. For me, it has become a practice of ritual, reflection, and gratitude. In a field where emotional boundaries can blur and cumulative loss is real, this ritual has helped me carry the work in a healthier way. It is a reminder that grief is not something to be avoided but something to be acknowledged and integrated into our work. For me, writing tributes has become a form of communication that bridges the clinical and the emotional.

My appreciation for writing deepened further and on a personal note when I recently experienced the loss of a mentor. Helping to write a tribute for him brought me back to the same principles I use when writing about my patients. It was a way of honouring his impact, of capturing the essence of who he was, and of processing my own grief. It reaffirmed for me that tributes matter because they allow us to continue the relationship in a different form, allow us to keep the person's spirit alive in our memories and honouring the impact they had and will continue to have on us.

Ultimately, communicating difficult news does not end with the moment we tell a family that their child has cancer or is dying. It continues in how we honour that child's life, how we support one another as a team, and how we make space for our own grief. Writing tributes has become one of the most meaningful ways I participate in this ongoing communication. It is a practice that honours the deceased, supports the living, and sustains me in the work I feel privileged to do, solidifying how important communication is for us as clinicians and as human beings.

References

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